

Boundary Characteristic Orthogonal Polynomials in One Variable

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Abstract

This paper is concerned with the procedure to generate boundary characteristic orthogonal polynomials (BCOPs) over the interval $[0, 1]$. First six orthogonal polynomials are generated with the help of a set of linearly independent functions satisfying the given boundary conditions. These orthogonal polynomials are controlled by two parameters which assume non-negative integer values and represent boundary conditions. Gram-Schmidt process has been used to generate the orthogonal polynomials. Furthermore, these orthogonal polynomials are converted into orthonormal polynomials. These polynomials have been tabulated for different values of controlling parameters. Two point boundary value problems representing free vibration of beams can be solved using these polynomials.

Keywords

Orthonormal Polynomials, Linearly Independent. Gram-Schmidt Process. Boundary Value Problems.

Introduction

Orthogonal polynomials have been used in numerical approximation for decades. These polynomials have applications in engineering, mathematics and physics. There has been tremendous growth in the application of orthogonal polynomials in solving boundary value problems. Orthogonal polynomials are a set of polynomials in which two polynomials are orthogonal to each other w.r.t. a specific inner product. These polynomials satisfy a three-term recurrence relation. Using this relation higher-order polynomials can be calculated. An infinite of orthogonal polynomials forms a complete basis for functions with the given inner product. Different families of orthogonal polynomials namely, Legendre polynomials, Hermite polynomials, Laguerre polynomials, Jacobi polynomials, orthogonal Bernstein polynomials and Chebyshev polynomials over different interval and the weight function are used.

The inner product of $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ is defined as follows:

$$\langle f, g \rangle = \int_a^b w(x) f(x) g(x) dx. \quad (1)$$

Two functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ are said to be orthogonal with respect to the weight function $w(x)$ on the interval $[a, b]$ if their inner product is zero.

A sequence of polynomials $\{\phi_m(x)\}$ is said to be orthogonal over the interval $[a, b]$ with respect to a weight function $w(x)$ if

$$\int_a^b w(x) \phi_m(x) \phi_n(x) dx = 0 \text{ for } m \neq n. \quad (2)$$

Objective of study

The objective of the study is to generate orthogonal polynomials and orthonormal polynomials in one variable that can be used as basis functions in the Rayleigh-Ritz method to solve boundary value problems.

Review of Literature

Researchers have used orthogonal polynomials in the solution of different types of problems of engineering, mathematics and physics. Many references are available in the literature on the use of orthogonal polynomials. Some well known references related to the theme are Szego [1939], Freud [1971], Askey [1975], Chihara [1978], Lal and Goel [2001], Hocine et al. [2007], Ismail [2013], Ahmadi and Nikkhoo [2014], Chakraverty and Behera [2014], Bhat [2015], Mirzaee and Samadyar [2017], Nanware [2021], Farzana et al. [2023] and Alomari et al. [2024].

The aim of this work is to generate boundary characteristic orthogonal polynomials over $[0, 1]$. Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization process is used to generate the orthogonal polynomials. These orthogonal polynomials satisfy boundary conditions on the end points of the interval $[0, 1]$. Corresponding orthonormal polynomials are also presented. These polynomials can be utilized by researchers analyzing the vibration problems in one dimension.

Main Text

Generation of Orthogonal polynomials

Let us consider the domain [0, 1]. To generate orthogonal polynomials, we start with the set $\{h_i\}$, where $h_i = g f_i, f_i = x^{i-1}, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ are linearly independent functions over the domain [0,1] and $g = x^p(1-x)^q$. The set such that it satisfies boundary conditions on $x=0$ and $x=1$.

Orthogonal polynomials $\{\phi_i\}$ are generated using a recurrence relation of the form

$$\phi_1 = h_1,$$

$$\phi_i = h_i - \alpha_{ij} \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \phi_j, i = 2, 3, \dots, n \tag{3}$$

where

Here the weight function $w(x)$ is assumed to be 1.

First six orthogonal polynomials can be written as given below

$$\phi_1 = x^p(1-x)^q$$

$$\phi_2 = x^{p+1}(1-x)^q - \alpha_{21}x^p(1-x)^q$$

$$\phi_3 = x^{p+2}(1-x)^q - \alpha_{32}x^{p+1}(1-x)^q - (\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})x^p(1-x)^q$$

$$\phi_4 = x^{p+3}(1-x)^q - \alpha_{43}x^{p+2}(1-x)^q - (\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32})x^{p+1}(1-x)^q - (\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})x^p(1-x)^q$$

$$\phi_5 = x^{p+4}(1-x)^q - \alpha_{54}x^{p+3}(1-x)^q - \{\alpha_{53} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\}x^{p+2}(1-x)^q - \{\alpha_{52} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\}x^{p+1}(1-x)^q - \left\{ \alpha_{51} - \alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} + \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \right. \\ \left. + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \right\}x^p(1-x)^q$$

$$\phi_6 = x^{p+5}(1-x)^q - \alpha_{65}x^{p+4}(1-x)^q - \{\alpha_{64} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\}x^{p+3}(1-x)^q - \{\alpha_{63} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\}x^{p+2}(1-x)^q - \left\{ \alpha_{62} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32} \right. \\ \left. + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32} \right\}x^{p+1}(1-x)^q - \left\{ \alpha_{61} - \alpha_{62}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{51} + \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} \right. \\ \left. + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \right\}x^p(1-x)^q$$

The orthonormal polynomials $\{\hat{\phi}_i\}$ are obtained by

$$\hat{\phi}_i = \frac{\phi_i}{\|\phi_i\|}, \quad \|\phi_i\|^2 = \int_0^1 \phi_i^2 dx. \tag{5}$$

The integrals $\int_0^1 x^p(1-x)^q dx$ are calculated in closed form using

$$\int_0^1 x^p(1-x)^q dx = \frac{p!q!}{(p+q+1)!}. \tag{6}$$

The first six orthogonal polynomials and corresponding orthonormal polynomials for different values of p and q are given below

(i) For $p = 0, q = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1 &= 1 \\ \phi_2 &= x - \alpha_{21} \\ \phi_3 &= x^2 - \alpha_{32}x - (\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{32}\alpha_{21}) \\ \phi_4 &= x^3 - \alpha_{43}x^2 - (\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32})x - (\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21}) \\ \phi_5 &= x^4 - \alpha_{54}x^3 - (\alpha_{53} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43})x^2 - (\alpha_{52} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32})x \\ &\quad - (\alpha_{51} - \alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} + \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21}) \\ \phi_6 &= x^5 - \alpha_{65}x^4 - (\alpha_{64} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54})x^3 - (\alpha_{63} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53})x^2 \\ &\quad - (\alpha_{62} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42})x \\ &\quad - \left(\begin{aligned} &\alpha_{61} - \alpha_{62}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{51} + \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} \\ &+ \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \\ &- \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \end{aligned} \right) \\ \hat{\phi}_1 &= \beta_{11} \\ \hat{\phi}_2 &= \beta_{21}x + \beta_{22} \\ \hat{\phi}_3 &= \beta_{31}x^2 + \beta_{32}x + \beta_{33} \\ \hat{\phi}_4 &= \beta_{41}x^3 + \beta_{42}x^2 + \beta_{43}x + \beta_{44} \\ \hat{\phi}_5 &= \beta_{51}x^4 + \beta_{52}x^3 + \beta_{53}x^2 + \beta_{54}x + \beta_{55} \\ \hat{\phi}_6 &= \beta_{61}x^5 + \beta_{62}x^4 + \beta_{63}x^3 + \beta_{64}x^2 + \beta_{65}x + \beta_{66}. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) For $p = 1, q = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1 &= x \\ \phi_2 &= x^2 - \alpha_{21}x \\ \phi_3 &= x^3 - \alpha_{32}x^2 - (\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})x \\ \phi_4 &= x^4 - \alpha_{43}x^3 - (\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32})x^2 - (\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})x \\ \phi_5 &= x^5 - \alpha_{54}x^4 - (\alpha_{53} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43})x^3 - (\alpha_{52} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42})x^2 \\ &\quad - \left(\begin{aligned} &\alpha_{51} - \alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} + \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} \\ &- \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \end{aligned} \right) x \\ \phi_6 &= x^6 - \alpha_{65}x^5 - (\alpha_{64} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54})x^4 - (\alpha_{63} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53})x^3 \\ &\quad - (\alpha_{62} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42})x^2 \\ &\quad - \left(\begin{aligned} &\alpha_{61} - \alpha_{62}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{51} + \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} \\ &+ \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \\ &- \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \end{aligned} \right) x \\ \hat{\phi}_1 &= \beta_{11}x \\ \hat{\phi}_2 &= \beta_{21}x^2 + \beta_{22}x \\ \hat{\phi}_3 &= \beta_{31}x^3 + \beta_{32}x^2 + \beta_{33}x \\ \hat{\phi}_4 &= \beta_{41}x^4 + \beta_{42}x^3 + \beta_{43}x^2 + \beta_{44}x \\ \hat{\phi}_5 &= \beta_{51}x^5 + \beta_{52}x^4 + \beta_{53}x^3 + \beta_{54}x^2 + \beta_{55}x \\ \hat{\phi}_6 &= \beta_{61}x^6 + \beta_{62}x^5 + \beta_{63}x^4 + \beta_{64}x^3 + \beta_{65}x^2 + \beta_{66}x \end{aligned}$$

(iii) For $p = 0, q = 1$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1 &= (1-x) \\ \phi_2 &= x(1-x) - \alpha_{21}(1-x) \\ \phi_3 &= x^2(1-x) - \alpha_{32}x(1-x) - (\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})(1-x) \\ \phi_4 &= x^3(1-x) - \alpha_{43}x^2(1-x) - (\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32})x(1-x) - (\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})(1-x) \\ \phi_5 &= x^4(1-x) - \alpha_{54}x^3(1-x) - (\alpha_{53} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43})x^2(1-x) - (\alpha_{52} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42})x(1-x) \\ &\quad - (\alpha_{51} - \alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} + \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})(1-x) \\ \phi_6 &= x^5(1-x) - \alpha_{65}x^4(1-x) - (\alpha_{64} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54})x^3(1-x) - (\alpha_{63} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53})x^2(1-x) \\ &\quad - (\alpha_{62} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42})x(1-x) \\ &\quad - \left(\begin{aligned} &\alpha_{61} - \alpha_{62}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{51} + \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} \\ &+ \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \\ &- \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \end{aligned} \right) (1-x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\phi}_1 &= \beta_{11}(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_2 &= \beta_{21}x(1-x) + \beta_{22}(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_3 &= \beta_{31}x^2(1-x) + \beta_{32}x(1-x) + \beta_{33}(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_4 &= \beta_{41}x^3(1-x) + \beta_{42}x^2(1-x) + \beta_{43}x(1-x) + \beta_{44}(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_5 &= \beta_{51}x^4(1-x) + \beta_{52}x^3(1-x) + \beta_{53}x^2(1-x) + \beta_{54}x(1-x) + \beta_{55}(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_6 &= \beta_{61}x^5(1-x) + \beta_{62}x^4(1-x) + \beta_{63}x^3(1-x) + \beta_{64}x^2(1-x) + \beta_{65}x(1-x) + \beta_{66}(1-x) \end{aligned}$$

(iv) For $p = 1, q = 1$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1 &= x(1-x) \\ \phi_2 &= x^2(1-x) - \alpha_{21}x(1-x) \\ \phi_3 &= x^3(1-x) - \alpha_{32}x^2(1-x) - (\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})x(1-x) \\ \phi_4 &= x^4(1-x) - \alpha_{43}x^3(1-x) - (\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32})x^2(1-x) - (\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})x(1-x) \\ \phi_5 &= x^5(1-x) - \alpha_{54}x^4(1-x) - (\alpha_{53} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43})x^3(1-x) - (\alpha_{52} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42})x^2(1-x) \\ &\quad - (\alpha_{51} - \alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} + \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})x(1-x) \\ \phi_6 &= x^6(1-x) - \alpha_{65}x^5(1-x) - (\alpha_{64} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54})x^4(1-x) - (\alpha_{63} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53})x^3(1-x) \\ &\quad - (\alpha_{62} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42})x^2(1-x) \\ &\quad - \left(\begin{aligned} &\alpha_{61} - \alpha_{62}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{51} + \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} \\ &+ \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \\ &- \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \end{aligned} \right) x(1-x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\phi}_1 &= \beta_{11}x(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_2 &= \beta_{21}x^2(1-x) + \beta_{22}x(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_3 &= \beta_{31}x^3(1-x) + \beta_{32}x^2(1-x) + \beta_{33}x(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_4 &= \beta_{41}x^4(1-x) + \beta_{42}x^3(1-x) + \beta_{43}x^2(1-x) + \beta_{44}x(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_5 &= \beta_{51}x^5(1-x) + \beta_{52}x^4(1-x) + \beta_{53}x^3(1-x) + \beta_{54}x^2(1-x) + \beta_{55}x(1-x) \\ \hat{\phi}_6 &= \beta_{61}x^6(1-x) + \beta_{62}x^5(1-x) + \beta_{63}x^4(1-x) + \beta_{64}x^3(1-x) + \beta_{65}x^2(1-x) + \beta_{66}x(1-x)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\beta_{11} &= \frac{1}{\|\phi_1\|}, \\ \beta_{21} &= \frac{1}{\|\phi_2\|}, \beta_{22} = \frac{-\alpha_{21}}{\|\phi_2\|}, \\ \beta_{31} &= \frac{1}{\|\phi_3\|}, \beta_{32} = \frac{-\alpha_{32}}{\|\phi_3\|}, \beta_{33} = \frac{-(\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})}{\|\phi_3\|}, \\ \beta_{41} &= \frac{1}{\|\phi_4\|}, \beta_{42} = \frac{-\alpha_{43}}{\|\phi_4\|}, \beta_{43} = \frac{-(\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32})}{\|\phi_4\|}, \\ \beta_{44} &= \frac{-(\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})}{\|\phi_4\|}, \\ \beta_{51} &= \frac{1}{\|\phi_5\|}, \beta_{52} = \frac{-\alpha_{54}}{\|\phi_5\|}, \beta_{53} = \frac{-(\alpha_{53} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43})}{\|\phi_5\|}, \beta_{54} = \frac{-(\alpha_{52} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42})}{\|\phi_5\|}, \\ \beta_{55} &= \frac{-(\alpha_{51} - \alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} + \alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21})}{\|\phi_5\|}, \\ \beta_{61} &= \frac{1}{\|\phi_6\|}, \beta_{62} = \frac{-\alpha_{65}}{\|\phi_6\|}, \beta_{63} = \frac{-(\alpha_{64} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54})}{\|\phi_6\|}, \beta_{64} = \frac{-(\alpha_{63} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53})}{\|\phi_6\|}, \\ \beta_{65} &= \frac{-(\alpha_{62} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32})}{\|\phi_6\|}, \\ \beta_{66} &= \frac{\left(\begin{aligned} &\alpha_{61} - \alpha_{62}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{63}\alpha_{31} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{51} + \alpha_{63}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{64}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} \\ &+ \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{52}\alpha_{21} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{41} - \alpha_{64}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \\ &- \alpha_{65}\alpha_{53}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{42}\alpha_{21} - \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{31} + \alpha_{65}\alpha_{54}\alpha_{43}\alpha_{32}\alpha_{21} \end{aligned} \right)}{\|\phi_6\|}.\end{aligned}$$

Result and Discussion

The coefficients α_{ij} for first six polynomials for different values of p and q are given in the tables (1-4). As far as the accuracy of the results is concerned it is noticed that.

$$\langle \phi_i, \phi_j \rangle \cong 10^{-17}, \quad i \neq j.$$

Table 1 Coefficients α_{ij} of orthogonal polynomials for $p = 0, q = 0$

j \ i	1	2	3	4	5
2	0.5				
3	0.33333	1			
4	0.25	0.9	1.5		
5	0.2	0.8	1.71429	2	
6	0.166667	0.714286	1.78571	2.77778	2.5

Table 2 Coefficients α_{ij} of orthogonal polynomials for $p = 1, q = 0$

j \ i	1	2	3	4	5
2	0.75				
3	0.6	1.33333			
4	0.5	1.42857	1.875		
5	0.428571	1.42857	2.5	2.4	
6	0.375	1.38889	2.91667	3.81818	2.91667

Table 3 Coefficients α_{ij} of orthogonal polynomials for $p = 0, q = 1$

j \ i	1	2	3	4	5
2	0.25				
3	0.1	0.666667			
4	0.05	0.428571	1.125		
5	0.0285714	0.285714	1	1.6	
6	0.0178571	0.198413	0.833333	1.81818	2.08333

Table 4 Coefficients α_{ij} of orthogonal polynomials for $p = 1, q = 1$

j \ i	1	2	3	4	5
2	0.5				
3	0.285714	1			
4	0.178571	0.833333	1.5		
5	0.119048	0.666667	1.63636	2	
6	0.0833333	0.530303	1.59091	2.69231	2.5

The coefficients β_{ij} for first six polynomials for different values of p and q are given in the tables (5-8).

Table 5 Coefficients β_{ij} of orthonormal polynomials for $p = 0, q = 0$

j \ i	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	1					
2	3.4641	-1.73205				
3	13.4164	-13.4164	2.23607			
4	52.915	-79.3725	31.749	-2.64575		
5	210	-420	270	-60	3	
6	835.789	-2089.47	1857.31	-696.491	99.4987	-3.31662

Table 6 Coefficients β_{ij} of orthonormal polynomials for $p = 1, q = 0$

$j \backslash i$	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	1.73205					
2	8.94427	-6.7082				
3	39.6863	-52.915	15.8745			
4	168	-315	180	-30		
5	696.491	-1671.58	1392.98	-464.327	49.7494	
6	2855.6	-8328.82	9085.99	-4542.99	1009.55	-75.7166

Table 7 Coefficients β_{ij} of orthonormal polynomials for $p = 0, q = 1$

$j \backslash i$	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	1.73205					
2	8.94427	-2.23607				
3	39.6863	-26.4575	2.64575			
4	168	-189	54	-3		
5	696.491	-1114.39	557.193	-92.8655	3.31662	
6	2855.6	-5949.16	4326.66	-1298	144.222	-3.60555

Table 8 Coefficients β_{ij} of orthonormal polynomials for $p = 1, q = 1$

$j \backslash i$	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	5.47723					
2	28.9828	-14.4914				
3	132.816	-132.816	28.4605			
4	576.75	-865.124	384.5	-48.0625		
5	2438.43	-4876.86	3325.13	-886.702	73.8918	
6	10152	-25380	23427.7	-9761.53	1774.82	-106.489

First six orthonormal polynomials are shown in figures 1 and 2 for $p=q=0$ and $p=q=1$ respectively.

Fig. 1 First six orthonormal polynomials for $p = 0$ and $q = 0$

Fig. 2 First six orthonormal polynomials for $p=1$ and $q=1$.

Conclusion

Orthogonal polynomials play important role in solving ordinary/partial differential equations. The BCOPs, satisfying boundary conditions, are used to approximate a given function on the domain $[0, 1]$. Such polynomials simplify the problem and minimize the chance of ill-conditioning. In this paper, first six BCOPs and corresponding orthonormal polynomials have been generated using the Gram-Schmidt process for different boundary conditions. Accuracy of the polynomials is also presented. Such polynomials find application in analysing transverse vibration of beams of uniform thickness. For a particular set of conditions at the boundary, these polynomials are generated once and can be used again and again without repeating the calculations.

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